

Title: Framing Vulnerability - EHCP Reform, Educational Rights, and the Risk of Rhetorical Erasure

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Abstract

This article provides a practice-led critique of recent government proposals to reform the Education, Health and Care Plan (EHCP) system in England. Drawing on professional experience as a school governor and educator, the paper examines how political discourse frames EHCPs as unsustainable and overused, thereby justifying policy shifts that could undermine legal protections for children with SEND. The article critically analyses this rhetoric and its implications, highlighting how it reframes entitlements as burdens and families as the problem, rather than the system. Through a governance case study and engagement with statutory frameworks, the article explores the civic and ethical responsibilities of governors and educational leaders to advocate for inclusive practice. The conclusion calls for further research into lived experiences of EHCP reform and the long-term impacts of weakening statutory safeguards. This contribution is relevant for practitioners, policymakers, and researchers concerned with educational equity, policy discourse, and rights-based governance.

Keywords SEND, EHCP reform, educational governance, inclusion, statutory rights, policy discourse

1. Policy Landscape and Reform Proposals

The current proposals for SEND reform in England are the culmination of several years of reviews, consultations, and ministerial briefings. Central to the government's case is the claim that the EHCP system has become overburdened, financially unsustainable, and inconsistent in delivery. Figures presented in recent DfE briefings highlight the rapid rise in EHCP applications, a trend ministers attribute to a 'culture of escalation' where families are incentivised to seek statutory plans in order to access basic provision (Department for Education, 2022).

This narrative has been reinforced by key ministerial statements. In July 2025, Catherine McKinnell, Minister for School Standards, appeared on LBC with Andrew Marr and described the EHCP system as a “one-way valve,” suggesting that once children entered the EHCP pathway, there was little movement back into mainstream provision without statutory support (McKinnell, 2025). While insisting that no current provision would be removed, she declined to confirm whether EHCPs would be retained in their current legal form, stating only that “it is perfectly possible EHCPs will stay.”

Parallel reporting in *The Guardian*, *Schools Week*, and *Special Needs Jungle* has revealed growing concern among sector leaders, families, and campaigners (Colman, 2025; Knight, 2023; Special Needs Jungle, 2025). These sources point to an emerging policy trajectory that may centralise decision-making, restrict parental choice, and replace enforceable entitlements with more ‘streamlined’ models, potentially reducing the statutory

weight of EHCPs. Critics argue that this reframing positions SEND support not as a legal right, but as a conditional resource to be managed within budget constraints.

While ministers have framed their proposals as empowering and evidence-led, much of the emphasis has been on controlling demand and curbing costs. Early intervention is cited as a preferred route, yet without parallel commitments to sustained funding, staff training, and universal inclusion frameworks, this remains aspirational (TES, 2025). The gap between political intent and systemic reality is at the heart of current sector anxiety.

In this context, understanding how language, assumptions, and economic rationales shape reform agendas becomes critical. The following section explores the legal context underpinning EHCPs and why their erosion represents not just administrative streamlining, but a fundamental shift in educational justice.

While the government's stated aim is to make SEND provision more consistent and accessible, many of the proposed changes risk undermining the legal infrastructure and statutory accountability that underpin EHCPs. By focusing heavily on demand management and "streamlining" processes, the policy discourse obscures the realities faced by families, many of whom already struggle to secure and enforce provision across educational transitions. These reforms arrive not into a vacuum, but into a system already marked by geographical inequality, high rates of tribunal challenge, and significant variation in local authority performance. As later sections will explore, the current direction of reform not only risks removing legal safeguards, but also reframes need as dependency, redirects blame toward families, and burdens schools with navigating reduced clarity and resource. These shifts must be understood not as isolated policy choices, but as part of a broader redefinition of rights, responsibility, and inclusion.

This paper is further underpinned by a critical-inclusive theoretical tradition that views educational policy not only as a tool for organising provision, but also as a site of

ideological production. Drawing on critical pedagogy and rights-based inclusion (Florian & Black-Hawkins, 2011), the analysis challenges dominant reform narratives that mask structural inequity through neutral-sounding discourse. It also engages with Foucault's (1980) framing of discourse as a mechanism of power, shaping which identities, claims, and actions are rendered legitimate within education systems. This theoretical lens enables a closer reading of how the EHCP system is being rhetorically repositioned, and what is at stake in that shift.

In line with Florian and Black-Hawkins' (2011) model of inclusive pedagogy, this paper challenges the assumption that SEND provision should be exceptional, conditional, or resource-dependent. Inclusive pedagogy asserts that teaching must be based on the idea that all learners are of equal value and that difference is an expected, ordinary aspect of human development. This stands in contrast to the emerging policy framing of EHCPs as extraordinary interventions justified only through tightly managed evidence or deficit. From this pedagogical standpoint, reforms that seek to reduce reliance on statutory plans must be scrutinised for whether they propose genuinely inclusive models, or whether they simply reallocate support without redistributing access or responsibility. For governors and practitioners, Florian and Black-Hawkins' principles offer a proactive lens: shifting from identifying 'who to support' toward designing systems that assume and welcome learner diversity as standard.

2. Legal and Statutory Context: The Foundations of the EHCP System

The Education, Health and Care Plan (EHCP) system was introduced under the Children and Families Act 2014, marking a significant shift in how support for children and young people with special educational needs and disabilities (SEND) was legislated and delivered in

England. Replacing the previous Statement of SEN system, EHCPs were designed to provide a more integrated, person-centred approach that brought together education, health, and social care within a single statutory document. Importantly, the Act embedded a legal duty on local authorities to secure the provision set out in an EHCP (Children and Families Act, 2014, Section 42), establishing enforceable rights rather than discretionary support.

Section 19 of the Act reinforces a rights-based ethos by requiring that local authorities have regard to the views, wishes, and feelings of the child and their parents, and actively support their participation in decision-making (Children and Families Act, 2014, Section 19). These provisions were introduced following widespread criticism of the former system's lack of accountability and its tendency to marginalise families. The EHCP framework, therefore, was not merely administrative reform, it was the legal articulation of an inclusive educational philosophy.

Any attempt to revise or replace EHCPs must therefore be seen not only in terms of bureaucratic efficiency or cost, but through the lens of legal precedent and moral obligation. Weakening the statutory weight of EHCPs, either by replacing them with non-binding documents or centralising their management in ways that reduce family agency, would mark a fundamental departure from the principles set out in the 2014 Act.

The introduction of The Education, Health and Care Plan (EHCP) system established robust statutory duties on local authorities to assess needs and secure provision. This legal duty is enforceable has been repeatedly confirmed in court. For example, in *R (JSH) v Westmorland and Furness Council* [2024] EWHC 3362 (Admin), the High Court issued a mandatory order compelling the council to provide the special educational provision specified in a 17-year-old's EHCP within five weeks. The judgment made clear that delays or omissions in provision constitute not just administrative failures, but actionable breaches of legal obligation.

Similarly, in *R (LW) v London Borough of Islington* [2025] EWHC 703 (Admin), a judicial review challenge concerning the legality of the EHCP process was dismissed only because the First-tier Tribunal offers a “suitable alternative remedy.” Importantly, the court reaffirmed the strength of statutory entitlements within the existing system and the legal mechanisms in place to uphold them.

These rulings are a stark reminder: the legal protections embedded in EHCPs are not symbolic, they are enforceable rights that hold authorities to account. Any move to replace EHCPs with non-statutory or discretionary frameworks would remove this enforceability, increasing the likelihood of unmet need and administrative inconsistency. This would be a direct reversal of the rights-based trajectory established by the Children and Families Act and supported by the SEND Code of Practice (DfE & DoH, 2015).

EHCPs were designed to correct the flaws of the former Statement system by embedding accountability and legal recourse into SEND provision. The EHCP system, for all its flaws, offers families a legal route to challenge inadequate provision and to hold local authorities to account. Weakening their statutory status risks returning to a fragmented landscape where access to support is based not on need, but on geography, advocacy strength, or luck. As such, reform proposals must be evaluated not simply for their administrative logic, but for their fidelity to principles of justice, inclusion, and the rights of the child. And as governors and practitioners, we must remain vigilant to how any such reform proposals might erode not only entitlements, but the legal frameworks that secure educational justice for the most vulnerable.

2a. Systemic Challenges for Families: Enforcement Across Transitions

Securing an EHCP is often just the first step. Families frequently face significant hurdles each time their child transitions between educational phases, such as from primary to secondary, or

into further education. A Department for Education (DfE) survey of over 13,000 parents reported that 17% of EHCPs took longer than the statutory 20-week legal time limit to finalise, with wide disparities in timeliness between local authorities. For families without a previous Statement of SEN, around 15% were required to submit more than one request before securing an EHCP (Department for Education, 2017).

Even after plans are issued, enforcement remains uneven. According to Contact, a leading charity for families with disabled children, 98% of tribunal appeals regarding EHCPs are successful. This figure highlights how frequently local authorities fail to uphold their legal responsibilities (Contact, 2023). However, pursuing redress through the tribunal system is both emotionally and financially taxing. In one survey, 41% of parents reported leaving employment to advocate for their child's entitlements, citing exhaustion, stress, and system complexity as major factors (SEND Action, 2024).

The impact of inadequate support is not only borne by parents. School avoidance among children with unmet SEND needs has risen significantly, with 60% of families reporting school anxiety or refusal, and 14% reporting exclusion or informal off-rolling as a consequence of delayed or withdrawn provision (Contact, 2023). These figures illustrate that EHCPs are not simply administrative tools. They are vital safeguards against educational marginalisation.

Evidence suggests that statutory SEND support through Statements and EHCPs leads to long-term benefits that extend far beyond immediate educational outcomes. The Department for Education's 2024 report on young adult outcomes shows that individuals with formal SEND plans are significantly more likely to engage in post-16 education or training and report better mental health and wellbeing (DfE, 2024). Economic studies, including BMC Public Health (Smith et al., 2015), link unmet SEND needs to a 62% reduction in lifetime earnings. Meanwhile, research by the Education Policy Institute (2021) finds that robust

SEND provision contributes to societal productivity and social cohesion. In short, EHCPs offer a compelling return on investment for individuals and society alike.

Any future reform must confront these realities. The issue is not just about over-identification or demand escalation, but about systemic fragility, inconsistencies in enforcement, and the immense personal cost borne by families. To remove or weaken the legal status of EHCPs without addressing these systemic failures would risk compounding injustice under the guise of efficiency.

In the current discourse around EHCP reform, the child is frequently framed as a passive object of provision, rather than an active participant in their own educational journey. This erasure is not simply an omission, but a discursive act that positions the child as voiceless within systems of control. Drawing on the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC, 1989), there is a statutory and ethical requirement to consider the child's views, wishes, and feelings, yet this principle is noticeably absent from public discourse on reform. Inclusive research practice, as articulated by MacBlain, Dunn, and Luke (2017), asserts that meaningful participation requires not just listening to the child, but reconfiguring adult-child relations to make space for agency. In this framing, the child is not simply the subject of EHCP processes, but a co-constructor of educational meaning and value.

Policy rhetoric, however, tends to instrumentalise the child, invoking their needs as justification for funding decisions, systemic efficiency, or early intervention schemes, while rarely offering space for their perspective. This risks reducing the child to a symbolic figure used to rationalise institutional agendas, rather than an individual with evolving capacities and rights. The implications of such positioning are significant: reforms that exclude children's voices from development and review processes risk further entrenching a deficit narrative, and may miss opportunities to co-design provision that reflects lived experience.

Reframing the child as agentive not only aligns with inclusive pedagogy, but challenges the top-down, managerial tone that dominates much current policy discussion.

This exclusion of the child's perspective is symptomatic of a broader pattern in SEND discourse, where systems are restructured around perceived efficiencies rather than relational or rights-based values. As MacBlain et al. (2017) argue, such patterns are often legitimised through adult-centric assumptions about competence, capability, and service delivery. In current policy debates, the child is often spoken for by proxy by parents, professionals, or institutions, but seldom positioned as a stakeholder with voice and evolving autonomy. This aligns with Foucault's concept of governmentality, where populations (including children) are managed through systems that construct categories of need and regulate access to support (Foucault, 1980).

Moreover, the reform rhetoric's emphasis on "streamlining," "dependency," and "over-identification" contributes to a framework in which the child's needs are rendered suspect or excessive unless verified through deficit-led evidence. This instrumentalises assessment processes, encouraging compliance with narrow diagnostic categories rather than holistic engagement with the child's lived experience. From a rights perspective, this undermines Article 12 of the UNCRC, which asserts that every child capable of forming a view has the right to express it freely in all matters affecting them. The selective visibility of the child, present in principle but marginal in practice reflects not only a policy failure but a discursive one: the inability of the system to accommodate voice that does not conform to managerial logics.

Reinstating the child as an epistemic subject within the EHCP framework would require more than tokenistic consultation. It would involve embedding child-led participatory mechanisms within assessment, review, and reform processes, and recognising their insights as both legitimate and necessary. In practical terms, this could mean involving children in the

co-design of learning environments, adapting review procedures to capture their perspectives authentically, and training adults to support communicative inclusion beyond verbal expression alone (Lundy, 2007). Without such structural and cultural shifts, children with SEND risk remaining rhetorically included but substantively excluded from the systems designed to support them.

3. Discourse and Framing: Analysing Government Language

This analysis adopts a practitioner-led, reflexive approach informed by Fairclough's model of Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA). As a school governor and educator, I draw upon situated knowledge to interpret language patterns through the lens of lived governance. This reflexivity, while not constituting a formalised research design, enhances the study's analytical depth by embedding it in the tensions between statutory obligation and rhetorical erosion. CDA, in this context, serves as both interpretive method and critical literacy tool, offering insight into how public discourse configures entitlement, blame, and the boundaries of inclusion (Fairclough, 2001; Luke, 2002).

In addition, CDA is used here to examine how political rhetoric around EHCP reform operates ideologically. CDA in this context offers a framework through which language can be interrogated not merely as a means of communication but as a mechanism for producing, reproducing, and legitimising social power. As Fairclough argues, discourse is both shaped by social structures and actively shapes them, making it a central site for understanding the dynamics of educational policy (Fairclough, 2001). Through this lens, phrases such as "demand explosion" and "escalation culture" are not neutral descriptors but discursive strategies that construct problem narratives and position families, practitioners, and children within constrained subjectivities (Gee, 2011).

As a media practitioner familiar with narrative construction and political framing, I recognise how phrases like “one-way valve,” and more recently, terms such as “demand explosion” and “escalation culture,” function not merely as descriptions, but as ideological tools. These terms have been used in policy-adjacent discourse, including statements reported by the County Councils Network and referenced in sector press such as *Schools Week*, where the escalation of EHCP requests is framed as a cultural or behavioural problem among parents and schools (Schools Week, 2024; IPSEA, 2023). This language operates to individualise responsibility, suggesting that families are creating pressure through overuse or strategic escalation, rather than responding to unmet need in an overstretched system. By doing so, it shifts the policy narrative away from accountability and underfunding, and toward user behaviour as the source of system dysfunction. In this framing, EHCPs are portrayed not as tools of justice or need-based planning, but as drains on resource and evidence of cultural malfunction. Such semantic shifts are not accidental; they mirror broader public sector reform strategies where rights-based entitlements are reimagined as threats to fiscal sustainability or systemic coherence (Knight, 2023).

For example, the term “demand explosion” suggests that parental requests for EHCPs are excessive and abnormal. It reframes need as burden, positioning families as the cause of pressure on the system rather than highlighting long-standing underfunding or inconsistent local provision. Similarly, describing the situation as an “escalation culture” implies that families and schools are acting strategically, or even manipulatively, to secure additional support. This subtly shifts blame away from structural failures, such as delayed early intervention or inconsistent mainstream SEND provision, and onto those seeking help. In this way, policy rhetoric creates a moral hierarchy, where families are viewed not as advocates responding to unmet need, but as opportunists undermining fairness (Fairclough, 2001; Knight, 2023).

This discursive tactic is neither new nor accidental. As Briant, Watson, and Philo (2011) have shown in the context of disability and welfare reform, negative framings often appear in times of austerity or system reform as a way to prepare the public for the withdrawal of rights. By presenting EHCPs as “unsustainable” or “inefficient,” the government cultivates a justification for policy change, even when evidence suggests that the system is already struggling to meet statutory obligations (Contact, 2023).

Drawing from framing theory (Entman, 1993; Fairclough, 2001), we also understand that to frame an issue is to select certain aspects of perceived reality and make them more salient, in ways that promote a particular problem definition, moral evaluation, or policy solution. Other examples of framing EHCPs as emblematic of "dependency" or "parental escalation," further serves to individualise the problem, portraying families as overzealous, schools as complicit, and support as a resource that must be reined in. The shift subtly transfers blame away from structural underfunding and systemic failures, instead placing it on users of the system.

Moreover, ministers’ use of ambiguity such as “we haven’t made a decision” or “it is perfectly possible EHCPs will stay” functions to normalise uncertainty (McKinnell, 2025). This rhetorical vagueness destabilises trust while gradually accustoming stakeholders to the possibility of removing legal safeguards, a strategy well-documented in crisis communication and political messaging (Entman, 1993).

This set of tactics aligns with long-standing media strategies used to manage public opinion in times of welfare reform, as seen in earlier portrayals of disability benefits and social housing (Briant, Watson, & Philo, 2011). These discourses often rely on binary oppositions ‘deserving’ vs. ‘undeserving’, ‘need’ vs. ‘misuse’ and function to fracture solidarity while making regressive policy palatable to the public.

As someone experienced in framing and media semiotics, I argue that this language does not merely reflect the system, it remakes it. Public discourse that casts need as excess, and rights as costs, lays the groundwork for policy that is less accountable, less inclusive, and more vulnerable to political convenience. In this context, challenging the rhetoric around EHCPs is not simply an academic or policy concern. It is a civic act of media literacy. It is essential to name these patterns and analyse them critically, because when the framing changes, the framework often follows, and the consequences are not theoretical, they are lived, material, and disproportionately affect the most vulnerable.

The language used by government ministers and advisers in public discussions of EHCP reform reveals more than policy intent, it shapes public understanding, institutional response, and ultimately policy direction. Certain rhetorical devices operate to redefine social norms and reposition systemic responsibility. Language is not neutral. It is a powerful actor in policymaking, capable of legitimising structural change through the subtle manipulation of metaphor, omission, and associative framing. As explored above, by framing EHCPs as excessive and the system as broken, the groundwork is laid for reforms that may limit entitlement and shift responsibility onto individuals rather than the state. It is therefore vital to challenge the underlying assumptions embedded in this rhetoric and to foreground the voices and experiences of those most affected.

4. Practitioner-Governor Reflection: The Wiggonby Case

As Chair of Governors at Wiggonby C of E School, I have witnessed first-hand the importance of EHCPs in securing targeted support for children with complex needs. In our small, rural context, every child's access to provision matters, and the processes surrounding EHCPs often represent a last line of legal defence for families navigating an overstretched system. While not all children with additional needs require an EHCP, for those who do, it is

often the only mechanism through which the necessary resources and accountability can be guaranteed.

As a small rural primary school, Wiggonby operates within tight resource constraints and relies heavily on statutory clarity to secure equitable provision. Our governing board, though deeply committed to inclusion, must frequently navigate uncertainty around funding and SEND access. The process of drafting a letter to our MP in response to proposed reforms became a moment of reflection on my dual role as both a governor and an experienced educator. The letter was presented to the Wiggonby C of E School governing board for discussion, offering a formal and practice-based expression of concern about the EHCP reform agenda and its implications for statutory entitlement and inclusive provision (Cooper, 2025). In this context, the draft letter served not only as advocacy but also as a formal artefact of the board's engagement with national reform discussions. This mirrors broader arguments about the civic function of school governance as a form of community-based educational leadership (Wilkins, 2015).

With over two decades in FE and HE, I have worked with students who simply, would not have achieved without the interventions secured through Statements of SEN and, more recently, EHCPs. These statutory mechanisms, as outlined in the SEND Code of Practice (Department for Education & Department of Health, 2015), provided structured access to support that has often enabled students to remain engaged in learning and make meaningful academic and social progress. It is the underpinning moral principles of these legal frameworks which enabled access to sustained support throughout schooling and beyond, often being the primary difference between disengagement and long-term educational progression. These students as such are not outliers or burdens on the system, they are contributors to society who simply needed time, trust, and support (Special Needs Jungle, 2025). In my experience, many of these students benefited not only from formal provision but

from educators who understood how to navigate and advocate within systems shaped by legal entitlement.

This is particularly relevant in small rural schools like Wiggonby, where governors often play a central role in interpreting policy in context, challenging provision gaps, and supporting leadership in a climate of constraint. Writing the letter to our MP, therefore, was not an isolated gesture, but an act shaped by over twenty years of working across post-16 and higher education, witnessing these first-hand the long-term consequences of early intervention or its absence. It was also an act of civic engagement through governance, aligning with arguments that school governors serve as connectors between educational institutions, democratic accountability, and community voice (James et al., 2010).

What emerged in this moment was a concern that SEND provision is once again being reframed, not as an entitlement to be strengthened, but as an expense to be managed. As governors, we are tasked with upholding the values of our school, safeguarding the rights of children, and holding systems to account. Speaking out on proposed reforms, particularly those that risk removing legal protection, is not a political act but a professional and ethical one. In contexts like ours, where resources are limited and rural schools often feel overlooked, the potential erosion of EHCPs represents a direct threat to inclusion (Colman, 2025).

At a recent SEND review subcommittee, a proposed policy draft referenced the need to “streamline over-allocation” of EHCPs; a phrase not found in statutory guidance, but directly mirroring phrasing used by national spokespersons. The phrase subtly reframed inclusive provision as excess rather than equity. This moment illustrated how national discourse seeps into local decision-making, even in well-intentioned contexts. For governing bodies, such moments require active interrogation, not only of policy drafts but of the

discursive frameworks that shape them. Without this scrutiny, inclusive intent may be undermined by the silent adoption of exclusionary assumptions.

At Wiggonby, several pupils identified as potential EHCP candidates have instead benefited from a proactive, integrated model of support including staff training, mental health interventions, and in-class differentiation. Under this inclusive governance approach, senior teachers and experienced teaching assistants delivered targeted sessions in emotional regulation, anxiety management, and social skills development. These initiatives, though not formal EHCPs have been embedded within everyday pedagogical practice. However, a number of these pupils, when later granted EHCPs due to complex or evolving mental health needs, required additional support in school, illustrating the inextricable link between mental health and SEND entitlement (Fazel et al., 2014).

This strategy reframes support not as isolated interventions but as structural inclusion, where mental health and learning needs are positioned centrally in curriculum planning. It reflects findings from OECD and Public Health England that embedding mental health services within schools boosts both wellbeing and educational outcomes (OECD, 2020). Crucially, this small-school approach highlighted how governors, by reinforcing rights-based pedagogy and redirecting resources internally, can counter national narratives that frame mental health support as over-prescription or resilience deficits.

These narratives mirror recent ministerial rhetoric, for example, Education Secretary Bridget Phillipson emphasised the importance of ‘grit’ and resilience while warning against "over-prescription" of mental health support in schools (The Guardian, May 2025). Such framing risks scaling back psychosocial interventions by recasting them as signs of weakness rather than legitimate needs. Our experience at Wiggonby demonstrates an alternative: one where small-scale, systemic adaptations not only address early mental health needs but also

safeguard long-term SEND provision by embedding inclusive practices rather than isolating support only to those with formal plans.

This section is a call for practitioner-governors and school leaders to recognise the power of their voice in shaping policy conversations. It is also an invitation to remember that SEND reform cannot be viewed in isolation from lived experience, local context, or legal accountability. While dominant narratives position EHCPs as a burden or evidence of parental escalation, they often obscure the civic labour enacted by parents, educators, and governors in sustaining rights-based provision. Through informal advocacy, public letters, tribunal appeals, and collective action, these actors engage in what Allan (2008) refers to as “micro-resistance” small, situated acts that contest dominant framings of inclusion and entitlement. Such resistance is vital in systems where formal language depoliticises structural failures and recasts legitimate need as misuse. This repositioning of practitioners and parents as active interpretive agents, not simply service users reflects a broader ethics of care that underpins inclusive educational practice (Slee, 2011).

5. Implications for Governance and Civic Accountability

The proposed reforms to the EHCP system present a defining moment for school governance. Governors, as stewards of both institutional accountability and community representation, are uniquely positioned to scrutinise the potential consequences of national policy on local practice. Yet historically, governing bodies have been underutilised in shaping or resisting education reform, particularly where statutory rights are at risk of dilution (Knight, 2023).

In the case of EHCPs, the potential shift from enforceable legal entitlements to discretionary models of support demands an assertive governance response. Boards must not only be aware of these changes but actively engage with their implications. This includes challenging assumptions within school improvement plans, scrutinising local authority

provision, and ensuring that any emerging models of support retain equity, transparency, and legal clarity. Where reforms threaten to erode statutory protection, governors must exercise their duty to advocate for vulnerable learners.

Beyond school-level governance, there is a wider civic responsibility to ensure that reform agendas do not proceed without critical scrutiny. As co-producers of education policy through engagement, representation, and challenge, governors can play a vital role in amplifying the voices of children and families. This involves engaging with MPs, contributing to consultations, and participating in broader debates about inclusion and justice (Department for Education, 2022).

In policy climates such as these, where statutory protections risk erosion through rhetorical shifts, the role of the governing body if required to shift away from only administrative duty. Governors must be prepared to monitor how national reform narratives translate into local decisions, ensuring that their school's culture, policies, and provision remain anchored in rights-based practice. This requires more than strategic oversight. It calls for more critical engagement with the assumptions behind policy changes, and an underlying willingness to scrutinise how language and systems might inadvertently normalise exclusion. Where necessary, this must include moving beyond passive compliance to active scrutiny, challenging decisions that restrict access to provision, interrogating patterns in SEND funding or placement, and engaging directly with local authorities when thresholds or support pathways shift without transparency.

Resilience to reform rhetoric must be built into the culture of governance itself. This can include scheduling regular scrutiny of EHCP processes and SEND outcomes as standing items on board agendas, ensuring governors receive training on the legal and social implications of reform, and fostering relationships with local SEND forums and family support networks. Importantly, governors must not underestimate their capacity for wider

civic influence. This may involve submitting public responses to consultations, seeking clarification from local MPs, or using the visibility of their position to raise community concerns. Recognising when procedural neutrality must give way to ethical leadership is part of the responsibility that comes with governance, particularly in small schools where marginal changes in policy interpretation can have disproportionate effects on children's futures.

The risk of rhetorical erasure, where the framing of policy conceals the withdrawal of rights, requires a governance culture that is legally literate, ethically grounded, and willing to speak with clarity and conviction. EHCP reform is not only a policy issue but a test of our collective commitment to educational integrity. In this moment, civic accountability must mean more than compliance; it must mean action.

What is often absent in these debates is the perspective of the child themselves. Within both policy rhetoric and system design, the child is frequently spoken for, positioned as either passive beneficiary or bureaucratic cost. A rights-based approach must reposition the child not only as the subject of provision but as a voice within it, seen, heard, and actively included in both planning and decision-making. As Slee (2011) argues, inclusion must extend beyond physical access to encompass the discursive and participatory positioning of the child as a rights-holder, not simply the subject of intervention.

6. Conclusion and Research Directions

The proposed reform of the EHCP system is not merely a technical adjustment within the SEND landscape. It represents a profound shift in how the state conceptualises educational need, accountability, and the rights of children. This paper has argued that the rhetorical reframing of EHCPs as excessive or unsustainable serves as a precursor to policy change that may weaken legal protections and reduce equitable access to support (TES, 2025).

By drawing on lived governance practice, statutory frameworks, and critical discourse analysis, this contribution makes the case for practitioner-led policy critique. It demonstrates how governors, particularly in rural or under-resourced settings, can act as ethical witnesses to reform processes that might otherwise proceed without challenge.

The original contribution of this paper lies in its fusion of critical discourse analysis with governance-level practice. By centring the role of the school governing body within the SEND reform landscape, it offers an underexplored perspective on how civic actors interpret and respond to national policy shifts. This paper advances the field by conceptualising governors not as passive implementers, but as knowledge-holders, interpreters, and ethical mediators in contested policy environments. In doing so, it bridges a gap between SEND scholarship and educational governance, and invites further research into how practitioner reflexivity can inform system-level resilience.

Further research is needed in several key areas. First, a deeper qualitative understanding of how families experience EHCP processes at the point of proposed reform would provide valuable insight into both systemic pressures and individual impacts. Second, the role of school governors as civic actors in education policy remains under-theorised and under-examined. Finally, longitudinal analysis of the outcomes of EHCP reform, particularly in relation to access, attainment, and equity, will be critical in assessing the long-term implications of any policy shift.

At a time when educational reform is increasingly driven by fiscal narratives, this work argues for a return to principles: of inclusion, rights, and justice. Policy rooted in these values does not fear legal accountability; it embraces it. It is incumbent on researchers, governors, and practitioners to insist that reforms enhance, rather than diminish, our collective commitment to every child's entitlement to a meaningful education.

References

Allan, J. (2008). *Rethinking inclusive education: The philosophers of difference in practice*. Springer.

<https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-1-4020-6093-9>

Briant, E. L., Watson, N., & Philo, G. (2011). *Bad news for disabled people: How the newspapers are reporting disability*. Strathclyde Centre for Disability Research.

Children and Families Act 2014, Part 3. London: The Stationery Office.

<https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2014/6/contents/enacted>

Colman, J. (2025, July 6). Government faces battle over SEND overhaul as campaigners voice fears. *The Guardian*.

<https://www.theguardian.com/education/2025/jul/06/government-faces-battle-over-send-overhaul-as-campaigners-voice-fears>

Contact. (2023). New figures show nearly all parents forced to go to SEND tribunal win.

Contact: For Families with Disabled Children.

<https://contact.org.uk/about-contact/news-and-views/new-figures-show-nearly-all-parents-in-england-forced-to-go-to-send-tribunal-win/>

Cooper, E. (2025, July). *Draft letter to MP regarding EHCP reform*. Unpublished manuscript, Wiggonby C of E School Governing Board.

Department for Education & Department of Health. (2015). *Special educational needs and disability code of practice: 0 to 25 years*.

<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/send-code-of-practice-0-to-25>

Department for Education. (2017). *Experiences of Education, Health and Care plans: A survey of parents and young people*. London: Department for Education.

https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5b040ddaed915d2ce621d4f7/Experiences_of_EHC_plans_-_A_survey_of_parents_and_young_people.pdf

Department for Education. (2022). *SEND Review: Right support, right place, right time*.

<https://www.gov.uk/government/consultations/send-review-right-support-right-place-right-time>

Department for Education. (2024). *Young adult outcomes for pupils with special educational needs: January 2025 update*. London: Department for Education.

https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/679b4f586bb4c44f0805e777/Young_Adult_Outcomes_for_Pupils_with_SEN_January_2025.pdf

Education Policy Institute. (2021). *Identifying pupils with special educational needs: SEND in England 2021*. London: Education Policy Institute.

https://epi.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/SEND-Indentification_2021-EPI.pdf

Entman, R. M. (1993). *Framing: Toward clarification of a fractured paradigm*. *Journal of Communication*, 43(4), 51–58.

Fairclough, N. (2001). *Language and Power* (2nd ed.). Routledge.

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/49551220_Language_and_Power

Fazel, M., Wolf, K., & Mendelson, S. (2014). *Mental health interventions in schools*.

Education in the Digital Age. OECD. <https://doi.org/10.1787/1209166a-en>

- Florian, L., & Black-Hawkins, K. (2011). Exploring inclusive pedagogy. *British Educational Research Journal*, 37(5), 813–828. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01411926.2010.501096>
- Foucault, M. (1980). *Power/Knowledge: Selected Interviews and Other Writings, 1972–1977*. Pantheon.
- Gee, J. P. (2011). *How to do discourse analysis: A toolkit*. Routledge.
<https://www.routledge.com/How-to-Do-Discourse-Analysis-A-Toolkit/Gee/p/book/9780415615853>
- The Guardian. (2025, May 16). ‘Grit’ no substitute for better mental health funding for pupils in England, say experts. <https://www.theguardian.com/education/2025/may/16/grit-no-substitute-for-extra-mental-health-funding-for-pupils-in-england-say-experts>
- IPSEA. (2023). *When children's rights become demands and parents get the blame*.
<https://www.ipsea.org.uk/blog/when-childrens-rights-become-demands-and-parents-get-the-blame/>
- James, C. R., Jones, J., Connolly, M., Brammer, S., Fertig, M., & James, J. (2012). The role of the chair of the school governing body in England. *School Leadership & Management*, 32(1), 3–19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13632434.2012.728094>
- Knight, S. (2023). The myth of EHCP misuse and what we risk by believing it. *Schools Week*.
<https://schoolswEEK.co.uk/the-myth-of-ehcp-misuse-and-what-we-risk-by-believing-it/>
- McKinnell, C. (2025, July 6). Interview with Andrew Marr. *LBC*.
<https://www.youtube.com/live/4nA4s1qRw4U?si=c0Nd2D-2E9E63782>
- Luke, A. (2002). Beyond science and ideology critique: Developments in critical discourse analysis. *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics*, 22, 96–110.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0267190502000051>
- Lundy, L. (2007). ‘Voice’ is not enough: Conceptualising Article 12 of the United Nations

- Convention on the Rights of the Child. *British Educational Research Journal*, 33(6), 927–942. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01411920701657033>
- MacBlain, S., Dunn, J., & Luke, I. (2017). *Contemporary Childhood: Theory, Policy and Practice*. Sage.
- OECD. (2020). *Embedding mental health services in schools is linked to enhanced student mental health and educational attainment*. Education in the Digital Age.
- R (JSH) v Westmorland and Furness Council* [2024] EWHC 3362 (Admin).
- R (LW) v London Borough of Islington* [2025] EWHC 703 (Admin).
- Schools Week. (2024). *Fierce SEND backlash begins as DfE sets sights on EHCPs reform*. <https://schoolsweek.co.uk/fierce-send-backlash-begins-as-dfe-sets-sights-on-ehcps-reform/>
- SEND Action. (2024). *Parent survey findings on the impact of securing and enforcing EHCPs*. SEND Action. <https://sendaction.org/latest-news/send-parent-survey-2024/>
- Slee, R. (2011). *The irregular school: Exclusion, schooling, and inclusive education*. Routledge. <https://www.routledge.com/The-Irregular-School-Exclusion-Schooling-and-Inclusive-Education/Slee/p/book/9780415479905>
- Smith, N., Taylor-Robinson, D., & Barr, B. (2015). *Impact of school dropout on health and economic outcomes: A longitudinal study of vulnerability and early disengagement*. *BMC Public Health*, 15(1), 1057. <https://bmcpublichealth.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12889-015-2400-8>
- Special Needs Jungle. (2025, May 24). Children with special needs in England may lose legal right to school support. <https://www.specialneedsjungle.com/gillian-keegan-education-secretary-pause-send-reform-plans-publish-send-review-responses/>
- TES. (2025, July). Tens of thousands of pupils with SEND needs ‘could be met without

EHCP'. <https://www.tes.com/magazine/news/specialist-sector/tens-thousands-pupils-send-needs-met-without-ehcp>

United Nations. (1989). *Convention on the Rights of the Child*.

<https://www.unicef.org.uk/what-we-do/un-convention-child-rights/>

Wilkins, A. (2015). Professionalizing school governance: The disciplinary effects of school governance reform in England. *Journal of Education Policy*, 30(2), 182–200.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/02680939.2014.941414>